

Thermal Ageing of VVER Reactor Pressure Vessel Steel

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Abstract. This paper investigates the effect of the annealing process in reactor pressure vessel steel of VVER-440 which can lead to structural recovery or thermal ageing. Two annealing experiments were performed to observe the boundary between these two processes as there is no strict known limit to the annealing temperature or time for that. This is preliminary study for the DELISA-LTO project, where the long-term thermal stress from operation at about 300°C will be simulated by accelerated artificial annealing at increased temperature 420 - 450°C. The experiment showed that the optimal recovery temperature ranges from 450°C to 500°C and the optimal recovery time was probably around 30 hours for our small-sized samples. Prolonged annealing beyond 60 hours reveals new structural deterioration and precipitate formation which can indicate a start of the thermal ageing.

INTRODUCTION

During the operation of VVER 440, the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) is loaded by temperatures of about 300°C and irradiation by neutron fluence around 10^{24} n/m² [1] for more than 40 years. The radiation damage of the RPV material is significantly visible due to mechanical properties worsening, but the effect of the temperature is not fully clear. On one side, higher temperature can improve mechanical properties due to recovery of radiation-induced defects. On the other side, during the long-term exposition at higher temperatures, the thermal ageing of steels can be visible by the change of configuration of structure as grain size changes and formation of precipitation, which is later visible as change of material strength [2, 3]. The boundary between these two thermal processes, recovery versus ageing, is not described. This paper observes the thermal stress in RPV steel to find a limit for recovery temperature and time. The research investigated small-sized samples, which probably need a lower annealing time for visible changes in microstructure compared to the whole RPV steel. This has not yet been assessed and the optimization of annealing times for small samples contra the thick wall components is missing. We assume differences only according to reference literature [4], which shows that the tempering usually depends on the wall thickness. Also, the ASTM documentation shows that “the tempering of RPV steel requires holding the material at a subcritical temperature for a minimum duration of 1.5 h for every inch” [5]. Thus, our research is probably more conservative as the structural changes can be shown earlier – after shorter annealing time.

In this paper, two annealing experiments are described – one with the evident process of structure recovery after a previous proton implantation and the second experiment with the annealing of samples without any previous experimental structural damage. The Positron Annihilation Spectroscopy (PAS) measurement, as the most sensitive technique to identify vacancy-type defects, was used to measure the different thermal loaded states of the VVER 440 RPV steel – 15Kh2MFAA. The PAS data are supplemented by Barkhausen Noise Measurement (MBN) which investigates the residual stress of the samples appearing as the presence of structural defects (open volume defects, dislocations, grain boundaries and precipitations). The two annealed experiments were observed in terms of finding a difference in recovery annealing and thermal ageing during the first hours of the annealing.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS AND TREATMENTS

The investigated material 15KhMFAA (chemical composition in Table 1) was gained from the non-irradiated RPV manufactured for Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) Greifswald Unit 7. The steel was cut into smaller samples with the

dimensions 10x10x0.2 mm by electric saw with water cooling. Then the samples were brushed and polished into the mirror level for positron annihilation measurements.

TABLE 1. Chemical composition of VVER-440 reactor pressure vessel steel – 15KhMFAA in % wt.

Cr	Mn	Mo	Ni	Si	C	V	S and P	Cu
2-2.5	0.3-0.6	0.6-0.8	max 0.4	0.17-0.37	0.11-0.16	0.25-0.35	max 0.015	max 0.08

The Positron Annihilation Lifetime Spectroscopy (PALS) technique is a sensitive non-destructive method detecting small vacancy defects, including mono- and di-vacancies. The positron lifetime represents the interval between the positron birth in the radioactive source ^{22}Na and positron annihilation in the sample's structure. Both events release photons which detectors can catch. The limiting concentration for a technique due to the resolution of equipment is 1 ppm. The PALS digital equipment at the Slovak Technical University of Bratislava was utilized for measurement [6]. Data from positron measurements were analyzed according to the Standard Trapping Model [7] in data analytics program LT9 [8], which divides the positron lifetime spectrum into three distinct components corresponding to the bulk material value: for defect-free iron ≈ 110 ps [7], structural defects between 150 – 500 ps and in-flight annihilation events that occur outside the sample (over 500 ps). The results from the analysis are shown in Mean Lifetime (MLT) values which increase with the defect volume/presence growth and are calculated from all three component.

Coincidence Doppler Broadening Spectroscopy (CDBS) is a further positron annihilation technique which focuses on observing and analyzing the annihilation energy spectrum. This method detects changes in the Gaussian-shaped annihilation spectrum due to a change in defects presence in the investigated material. The spectrum peak (referred to as the S parameter) increases with either the size or concentration of defects. Furthermore, the chemical environment surrounding the annihilation site influences the spectrum, as evidenced by variations in the wings area of the spectrum (referred to as the W parameter). By comparing the W parameter to reference spectra of different chemical elements, the presence of specific chemical elements near the vacancy defects can be confirmed. CDBS measurements were conducted using semiconductor detectors cooled with liquid nitrogen [9]. Data analysis was performed using the CDBTool software [10].

The samples of 15Kh2MFAA underwent investigation using the Barkhausen noise (MBN) technique to assess residual stress formation during the annealing process. The Barkhausen noise measurement relies on the movement of Weiss domains within an external magnetic field, where structural defects can impede domain movement and hinder the magnetization process [11]. As the presence of defects (predominantly immobile defects) increases due to mechanical or thermal strain, residual stress within the structure also increases, resulting in a decrease in MBN values. A magnetizing frequency of 150 Hz and a magnetizing voltage of 2Vpp were utilized for the measurements. The results are presented in Barkhausen Noise amplitudes (BNA) and Root-Mean-Square (RMS) values, which are proportional to the magnetization properties of the material.

The first annealing experiment (more details in [12]) included the optimization of recovery temperature for 15KhMFAA steel after proton implantation with radiation damage up to 1 DPA, which simulated the collision cascade due to neutron flux to the material and formation of Frenkel pairs inside of that. After the irradiation, the sample was subsequently annealed for 2 hours at 200, 300, 400, 450 and 500°C in high vacuum. The sample was then measured by PALS technique.

The second annealing experiment compares the as-received sample and the sample annealed at 450°C for 30 and 60 hours. These annealing conditions were used for artificial thermal ageing which according to equation (1) are equivalent to thermal ageing during the operation for 113 days (30 h annealing) and 227 days (60 h annealing) at a temperature of about 300°C. This temperature will be applied within the DELISA-LTO project for investigation of the thermal resistance of the VVER construction materials in long-term operation. The equation (1) compares annealing times t_1 at temperature T_1 and annealing time t_2 at temperature T_2 , where Q is Arrhenius activation energy and R is the gas constant.

$$t_1/t_2 = \exp [Q/R (1/T_1 - 1/T_2)] \quad (1)$$

Within the second experiment, the sample was subsequently examined using PALS, CDBS, and MBN techniques to ascertain structural stress and deformation, specifically vacancy-type defects. The PALS results are presented in values of normalized mean lifetime to the reference as-received sample.

RESULTS

Results from the first experiment are shown in Fig.1 by the normalized Mean lifetime to the reference as-received sample. The MLT values confirmed the existence of the vacancy defects in the structure after the proton implantation, which was visible by the increase of the normalized MLT value up to 1.08. Consequently, the defects were partially annealed out as the temperature of the annealing was increasing and the best recovery was between 400 and 500°C. The normalized MLT decreased for the annealing process, but there was no full recovery probably due to short time as the minimal value of the normalized Mean lifetime was around 1.05.

After the annealing at over 500°C, the nucleation and growth of carbide/nitride precipitates started as was published also in [13], which brought into the structure new residual stress and defects. The normalized MLT value was there 20% higher than in the as-received sample and about 15% higher than in the recovered sample.

The structure was recovered along the step change of temperature from 200 to 500°C during the summary time of 10 hours. Further annealing at a higher temperature for the next 2 hours can be considered a negative influence of thermal annealing due to exceeding the optimal temperature.

FIGURE 1. The first annealing experiment [12]: The dependency of the normalized Mean lifetime to the as-received sample on the annealing temperature.

The results from the second experiment (Fig.2) are presented again as the normalized MLT values to the reference as-received samples for better comparison of the experiments. The normalized MLT after the 30 hours of annealing at 450°C, which is the optimal temperature for recovery, showed a significant decrease in its value. It can be explained by the recovery of structure from the open volume defects formed during the manufacturing of the steel and sample preparation. However, after further annealing during the next 30 hours (to summarize annealing time of 60 hours), the defects started to be formed again as the normalized MLT increased. This could be an observation of the border between the recovery of structure and the process of thermal ageing.

FIGURE 2. The dependency of the normalized Mean lifetime to the as-received sample on the annealing time.

The PALS results for the second annealing experiment were confirmed by MBN measurement (Fig. 3), where the RMS and BNA values responded to residual stress releasing after the 30 hours of annealing and residual stress accumulation after the 60 hours of annealing.

FIGURE 3. The change of Magnetic Barkhausen Noise values – Root-Mean-Square (RMS) and Barkhausen Noise Amplitude (BNA) with the annealing time increase.

The last applied technique CDBS within the second experiment showed that the samples after the annealing for 30 and 60 hours had a lower presence of defects, as is evident from the lower S parameter (Fig 4) shown as the ratio to

the reference as-received sample. However, they probably have a completely different surrounding of the defect than the as-received samples. This is assumed according to the different behavior of the W ratio for both annealed samples corresponding probably to precipitate formation around the defects. At the same time, the sample annealed during the longer time of 60 hours reported a bigger difference in spectra, thus, we assume the increase of precipitation concentration with the annealing time growth.

FIGURE 4. CDBS results showing the ratio of S and W parameter to the reference as-received sample.

CONCLUSION

This paper compared the annealing processes in terms of their ability to material recovery or the effect of thermal ageing. There is no strictly defined border between these processes, however, we tried to find it. Two annealing experiments observing the annealing temperature and time for structure recovery were performed. The optimal temperature for recovery was between 450 and 500°C found during the annealing time of up to 10 hours. For 30 hours of annealing at 450°C, another structural recovery was visible, however after 60 hours the worsening of the structure was found. This can indicate the existence of the border between the recovery process and thermal ageing, which should be further studied in more samples and for more annealing time points. After 30 and 60 hours of annealing, the formation of precipitates is assumed which worsens the structure and later this can have an influence on the mechanical properties.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was funded by the European Commission—Project DELISA-LTO (No.101061201).

REFERENCES

1. V. Slugen and J. Borak, „Monitorovanie životnosti tlakovej nádoby reaktora V-213”, *Jaderná energie* **1** (66), 54-61 (2020).
2. W. Wang, S. Liu, G. Xu, B. Zhang and Q. Huang, *Nucl. Eng. Technol.* **48**, 518-524 (2016).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.net.2015.11.004>
3. B.P. Liu, F.J. Meng, Z.M. Zhang, L. Li, J. Chen, H.L. Ming, J.Q. Wang, E.H. Han and W. Ke, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A* **856**, 143952 (2022).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2022.143952>
4. C. Li, L. Han, G. Yan, Q. Liu, X. Luo and J. Gu, *J. Nucl. Mater.* **480**, 344-354 (2016).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2016.08.039>
5. *Standard Specification for Quenched and Tempered Vacuum treated Carbon and Alloy Steel Forgings for Pressure Vessels*, ASTM A508/A508M-04 (ASTM, Pennsylvania, USA, 1995/ reapproved 2017), pp. 1-8.
https://doi.org/10.1520/A0508_A0508M-04
6. M. Petriska, S. Sojak and V. Slugen, *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **505**, 012044 (2014).
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/505/1/012044>
7. R. Krause-Rehberge and S.H. Leipner, *Positron annihilation in Semiconductors* (Springer, Berlin Germany, 1998).
8. J. Kansy, *Nucl. Instr. Meth. Phys. Res. A* **374**, 235 (1996).
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-9002\(96\)00075-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-9002(96)00075-7)
9. M. Petriska, V. Sabelova, V. Slugen, S. Sojak, M. Stacho and J. Veternikova, *Phys. Proc.* **35**, 117-121 (2012).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phpro.2012.06.021>
10. M. Petriska, V. Sabelova and V. Slugen, *Defect and Diffusion Forum (Trans. Tech. Publication)* **373**, 71-74 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/DDF.373.71>
11. T. Garstka, *J. Achieve. Mat. and Manufact. Engin.* **27**, 47 (2008).
12. V. Slugen, T. Brodziansky, J. S. Veternikova, S. Sojak, M. Petriska, R. Hincá and G. Farkas, *Materials* **15**, 7091 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15207091>
13. J. S. Veternikova, M. Hupka, S. Sojak, M. Petriska and V. Slugen, “An effect of manganese and nickel in VVER-440 reactor pressure vessel steels during the process of annealing”, in *APCOM 2023, AIP Conference Proceedings* 3054, edited by J. Vajda, J. Sitek and I. Jamnicky (AIP Publishing, Online, 2024), 050012.
<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0187478>